

24th October 2011

To: EUPHRESKO-II Governing Board

cc. Project Office

Dear Colleagues,

Re: EUPHRESKO-II Governing Board Representatives on Project Advisory Board

As you will know, EUPHRESKO-II only has a 'virtual' governing board (GB) and it is not currently intended that this will meet formally. However, we need to have 3–5 GB members represent the GB on a project advisory board (PAB). This PAB will also comprise representatives of EPPO, EFSA and SANCO in addition to the 3–5 GB members. We intend that the PAB members will attend the annual project meetings at 12, 24 and 36 months (funds have been specifically made available for this).

For more information on the roles of the GB and the PAB, see Annex 1 to this letter.

Please could you each consider and suggest people from the wider 'virtual' governing board membership (Annex 2) who you think would be appropriate individuals to serve on the project advisory board. Please also consider whether you yourself would be willing to take on this role, representing the GB on the PAB.

I'd be grateful for your responses via the EUPHRESKO project office by Friday 4th November 2011
euphresco@fera.gsi.gov.uk

To help you with your deliberations, here are some possible attributes you might consider when nominating others or yourself:

- Links to bodies such as COPHS, SCAR, EPPO
- Experience with other ERA-Nets
- Links to relevant Joint Programming Initiatives (e.g. FACCE-JPI)
- Balance between north, south, east and west Europe
- Balance between old and new EUPHRESKO Partners
- Availability now (EUPHRESKO-II) and potentially for the longer-term network.

Yours sincerely,

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Annex 1: Governance arrangements for EUPHRESKO-II (taken from the Project's Description of Work) - roles and responsibilities of the GB and PAB

The Governing Board (GB)

This will be a high level, over-arching steering group composed of a leading representative from the Ministry of each participating country or partner, as appropriate. Governing Board members for partners in the first EUPHRESKO Project are expected to continue in this role; GB members for new countries/partners will be established within 3 months of the Project start. Each member will also have a designated deputy. The GB will be responsible for overseeing and advising on the Network's strategic direction, reviewing the progress of the Network, and reviewing and endorsing specific outputs.

The GB will be chaired by the representative from the coordinating country (UK-Defra). The Coordinator will provide the secretariat.

The GB will be a 'virtual' group given the large number of partners and the costs involved in holding annual GB meetings. However:

- The 6-monthly reports prepared for the Commission will also be provided to the GB with additional indications of any specific issues requiring the GB to consider and/or act upon.
- The GB will also be supported and advised by a Project Advisory Board (see below).
- The GB may meet (without cost to the EUPHRESKO-II Project), if found necessary (e.g. back-to-back with COPHS meetings). This may be important if the Lisbon Treaty affects the long-term position of the European Commission's Standing Committee on Plant Health (i.e. it becomes replaced by smaller expert working groups), such that the COPHS might become more engaged in decision making and may have its own working groups (one of which could be the EUPHRESKO-II Governing Board for the long-term research funders network).

The Project Advisory Board (PAB)

This will be composed of 3–5 GB members (where possible including at least one SCAR representative). Additionally, it will include representatives from the three advisory bodies (the European Commission's DG SANCO; EPPO; and EFSA. Additionally, connections will be made to the Annexes Working Group of DG SANCO's Standing Committee on Plant Health. This Working Group is composed of technical experts and we will invite them to provide at least one person to participate on the PAB. We will also explore having a representative from COPA involved and/or a link to a potential SANCO Stakeholder Advisory Group that may emerge from the review of the Community Plant Health Regime. The PAB will attend the annual Project meetings and report back to the wider GB. The expert advisory bodies will also be able to advise the GB and the Project directly.

Annex 2: EUPHRESKO-II Governing Board Members

GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS

No.	Participant organisation name	Country	GB Member 1	Email
1	Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, Food & Environment Research Agency (DEFRA-FERA) - COORDINATOR	UK	Martin Ward	martin.ward@fera.GSI.GOV.UK
2	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment & Waste Management (BMLFUW)	Austria	Elfriede Fuhrmann	elfriede.fuhrmann@lebensministerium.at
4	The Federal Public Service for Public Health, Food Chain Security & Environment (FPS)	Belgium	Dominique Vandekerchove	dominique.vandekerchove@health.fgov.be
7	Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry, National Service for Plant Protection (NSPP)	Bulgaria	Olia Karadjova	oliakaradjova@abv.bg
8	Ministry of Agriculture (MZe)	Czech Rep	Ladislav Jerabek	ladislav.jerabek@mze.cz
9	The Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation (DASTI)	Denmark	Niels Gøtke	nigoe@fi.dk
10	Ministry of Agriculture, Research and Development Department (MARDD)	Estonia	Kylli Kaare	kylli.kaare@agri.ee
11	Ministry of Agriculture & Forestry (MMM-FI)	Finland	Martimo Tiina-Mari	Tiina-Mari.Martimo@mmm.fi
12	Ministry of Agriculture, Food, Fisheries & Rurality, General Food Directorate (MAAP-DGAL)	France		
14	The Federal Agency for Agriculture and Food (BLE)	Germany	Elke Saggau	ELKE.SAGGAU@ble.de
15	Julius Kühn Institute (JKI)	Germany	Jens Unger	jens-georg.unger@jki.bund.de

16	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece	Irene Vloutoglou	i.vloutoglou@bpi.gr
17	Department of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (DAFF)	Ireland	James Choiseul	James.Choiseul@agriculture.gov.ie
18	Ministry of Agricultural & Forestry Policy (MiPAAF)	Italy	Alberto Masci	a.masci@politicheagricole.gov.it
19	Ministry of Agricultural & Forestry Policy (MiPAAF)	Italy	Maria Montedoro	m.montedoro@politicheagricole.gov.it
20	Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)	Lithuania	Zita Duchovskiene	ZitaD@zum.lt
21	Ministry of Economic Affairs, Agriculture and Innovation, Department of Agrochains and Fisheries (EL&I)	Netherlands	Eric Regouin	e.j.m.regouin@minlnv.nl
23	Instituto Nacional de Recursos Biológicos (INRB)	Portugal	Dra. Fátima Calouro	fatima.calouro@inrb.pt
24	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (MAFF)	Slovenia	Jana Erjavec	jana.erjavec@gov.si
25	Ministry of Education and Science, National Institute of Agricultural Research (INIA)	Spain	Anabel de la Pena	anaisabel.delapena@inia.es
26	Federal Office of Agriculture, Division of Research & Extension (FOAG)	Switzerland	Gabriele Schachermayr	gabriele.schachermayr@blw.admin.ch
27	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs, DG of Agriculture Research (MARA-GDAR)	Turkey	Alev Burcak	aburcak@tagem.gov.tr
30	National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine (NAAS)	Ukraine	Dr. Olexandr Medvedovskiy	mishelleuaan@yandex.ru
31	All-Russian Plant Quarantine Centre (FGU VNIKR)	Russia	Natallya Sherokolava	natalia_sh@mail.ru